

D3.1 Digital Twin Framework

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Executive Summary

This report introduces a modular digital twin framework for batteries, integrating three key components: COLD for metamodeling, GLEANED for data harvesting, and ECHOED for digital twin orchestration. Together, these tools provide a robust solution for battery analysis, real-time monitoring, and performance prediction.

COLD establishes standardized battery metamodels using class-based definitions validated via Pydantic, ensuring structural consistency and semantic interoperability. These models can be serialized into JSON-LD, enabling integration with broader digital ecosystems. Predefined templates, like the CR2032 cell, support reuse while allowing for custom extensions.

GLEANED enables efficient data harvesting from static files (e.g., CSV, Parquet) and live sources (e.g., system monitoring via WMI). Its DataHarvester class facilitates static data ingestion, interval-based live polling, and continuous data streaming. The modular design ensures scalability and supports additional data sources as needed.

ECHOED serves as the orchestration layer, combining battery metamodels with real-world data to create dynamic digital twins. Through the DigitalTwin class, users can retrieve live status snapshots, analyze historical data, and monitor real-time updates. This integration transforms digital twins into actionable representations of physical batteries.

The framework has been validated through case studies involving historical file ingestion and live WMI-based monitoring, demonstrating its reliability, scalability, and adaptability. Its modular architecture ensures ease of integration with simulations, IoT systems, and machine learning models.

Future developments will include predictive capabilities, expanded data source integrations, and user-friendly interfaces for visualization and analysis. This framework positions itself as a powerful tool for advancing battery research, enabling better monitoring, lifecycle management, and performance optimization.

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
CC-CV	Constant Current Constant Voltage
EMMO	Elementary Multiperspective Materials Ontology
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FOOPS	FAIR Ontology Pitfall Scanner
PyBaMM	Python Battery Mathematical Modelling
RDF	Resource Description Framework
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WMI	Windows Management Instrumentation

1. Introduction

The rapid development of energy storage technologies, particularly batteries, has necessitated tools that enable real-time monitoring, efficient data management, and predictive capabilities to optimize performance and reliability. A digital twin – a virtual representation of a physical system – is increasingly recognized as a critical enabler for these goals. By combining data-driven insights, metamodel-based descriptions, and simulation tools, digital twins allow researchers and engineers to observe, understand, and predict battery behavior under various operating conditions. This report presents the development of a modular and extensible digital twin framework for batteries, comprising three integrated components: COLD, a metamodeling framework for describing battery systems and components; GLEANED, a data harvesting framework that gathers both live and static data; and ECHOED, the orchestration layer that brings together the metamodel and real-world data into a functional digital twin.

The creation of this framework was driven by the need for a unified and adaptable system to address diverse battery testing and operational requirements. Traditional battery data management workflows often suffer from fragmented data sources, inconsistent data structures, and manual processes that limit their usability. For example, data may exist as static files from laboratory experiments, live operational logs from equipment monitoring systems, or real-time data streams during field operation. Without a structured approach to integrating this information, the ability to analyze, visualize, and simulate battery performance is significantly reduced. To overcome these challenges, we developed a system that enables seamless data integration and real-time monitoring while remaining modular, user-friendly, and scalable.

At the core of the framework lies COLD, which provides standardized representations of battery systems using class-based models. This ensures that batteries are described consistently, allowing the digital twin to operate on well-defined parameters such as design capacity, chemistry, and key dimensions. Coupled with this, GLEANED serves as the data management backbone, responsible for collecting and managing both live and static data. It supports a variety of sources, including files such as CSV, Parquet, or JSON, as well as live streams, such as WMI-based data from Windows systems. By supporting both types of inputs, the framework provides a bridge between historical test data and real-time operational monitoring. Finally, ECHOED, the digital twin framework itself, ties these elements together. It creates a flexible interface for researchers and engineers to instantiate battery twins, retrieve live performance metrics, harvest static test results, and dynamically analyze data to make informed decisions.

The development of this digital twin framework is aimed at streamlining the workflows for battery testing, modeling, and monitoring while providing the tools for predictive analysis and real-world validation. The modular architecture enables it to be customized for different battery chemistries, testing protocols, and operational environments,

making it adaptable to both research and industrial applications. This report outlines the design and implementation of the three constituent components – COLD, GLEANED, and ECHOED – and demonstrates how they work together to enable the creation of digital twins for batteries.

1.1 Access to Framework Resources

The latest versions of the resources described in this report are available under the DigiBatt organization on GitHub: <https://github.com/DigiBatt>. The names of the packages (COLD, GLEANED, and ECHOED) are tentative, as they are under active development and may be subject to change prior to the first stable release. Please check the GitHub organization first, for the most up-to-date information.

2. Digital Twin Framework Design

The design of the digital twin framework revolves around the integration of well-structured battery metamodels with dynamic and static data sources to enable seamless digital representations of physical battery systems. The aim is to provide an adaptable, modular, and extensible environment where data can flow between the physical and virtual twins to support real-time monitoring, historical data analysis, and predictive simulation. To achieve this, the digital twin framework brings together three distinct components—COLD, GLEANED, and ECHOED—each of which plays a specific role in the architecture.

At the foundation lies COLD, a metamodeling framework responsible for describing the structure and properties of batteries in a standardized and semantic manner. Batteries are complex systems that consist of multiple components such as electrodes, electrolytes, separators, and cases, each of which may have specific properties relevant for analysis. These components, along with battery-level attributes like capacity, chemistry, and voltage ratings, are captured using class-based models in COLD. By leveraging Pydantic, COLD allows the creation of predefined templates for common battery types, such as the CR2032 coin cell or lithium-ion pouch cells, while also offering flexibility for customization. These models can be serialized into JSON-LD, ensuring that the descriptions adhere to semantic standards and can be easily shared or integrated with external systems. As a result, COLD provides a robust foundation for the digital twin, defining its parameters and establishing the connection between the virtual and physical representations of a battery.

While COLD establishes the structure of the twin, GLEANED plays the role of a data management and harvesting framework that enables the digital twin to interface with real-world data. In any digital twin system, the availability and quality of data are critical for accurate analysis and prediction. GLEANED addresses this need by providing tools to

collect, process, and manage data from multiple sources. It supports both static and live data, allowing users to work with historical records as well as real-time measurements. For static data, GLEANED can ingest common file formats such as CSV, Parquet, and JSON, which are often used to store experimental results or operational logs. For live data, GLEANED integrates with sources such as Windows Management Instrumentation (WMI) to monitor key performance parameters like voltage, charge rates, and remaining capacity in real time. GLEANED's modular design makes it possible to extend its capabilities to other data sources, such as external APIs, databases, or IoT devices, ensuring that the digital twin can adapt to diverse operational environments. The harvester class within GLEANED provides a unified interface for registering and managing data sources, enabling users to seamlessly switch between static analysis, live monitoring, and continuous data harvesting.

Building upon these two components, ECHOED serves as the orchestration layer that brings together the metamodel and data sources to form a fully functional digital twin. The core functionality of ECHOED lies in its ability to connect the virtual structure of the battery, as described by COLD, with the real-world data collected by GLEANED. This connection enables users to instantiate a digital twin that mirrors the behavior and performance of a physical battery system. The ECHOED framework provides a user-friendly interface for managing and interacting with digital twins. Users can create a twin by selecting or defining a metamodel and linking it with one or more data sources. Once instantiated, the twin can perform a variety of tasks, such as harvesting static data for analysis, continuously monitoring live performance, or retrieving snapshots of live status at specified intervals.

The design of ECHOED ensures that the digital twin is not just a static representation of the battery but an active, data-driven entity that evolves alongside its physical counterpart. For example, a user can configure the digital twin to monitor real-time voltage and capacity values from a live data source while simultaneously analyzing historical test results stored in a Parquet file. This ability to combine data from multiple sources provides a holistic view of the battery's performance, enabling users to identify trends, detect anomalies, and validate simulation results. ECHOED also includes mechanisms for flexibility and scalability. Data sources can be dynamically registered or removed, allowing the twin to adapt to changing requirements or testing environments. Moreover, the modular architecture of the framework makes it easy to extend its capabilities, whether by incorporating new types of metamodels, integrating with additional data harvesting tools, or connecting with battery simulation and optimization frameworks.

In addition to its core functionality, the design of ECHOED emphasizes usability and accessibility, ensuring that the framework can be adopted by both researchers and practitioners. The interface for interacting with the digital twin is intuitive, allowing users to perform complex operations such as live monitoring or static analysis with just a few

lines of code. This simplicity lowers the barrier to entry for using digital twins in battery research and development while maintaining the flexibility needed for advanced use cases. Furthermore, by adhering to standard data formats and semantic models, the framework promotes interoperability with other tools and systems in the battery ecosystem, such as simulation software, optimization frameworks, and ontological knowledge bases.

In summary, the design of the digital twin framework reflects a deliberate effort to combine structured battery metamodels with robust data harvesting capabilities into a cohesive and scalable system. COLD provides the foundation for describing battery systems in a standardized manner, GLEANED enables seamless integration of real-world data, and ECHOED orchestrates the interaction between these components to deliver a functional and user-friendly digital twin. This modular architecture ensures that the framework is adaptable to various battery types, data sources, and operational scenarios, making it a powerful tool for real-time monitoring, analysis, and predictive modeling of battery systems. By bridging the gap between physical measurements and virtual analysis, the digital twin framework lays the groundwork for improved battery performance, reliability, and innovation.

3. Implementation and Development

The implementation of the digital twin framework was undertaken through the careful design and integration of its three primary components: COLD, GLEANED, and ECHOED. Each component was developed to address specific functionalities required to create a robust and adaptable system for battery data management and digital twinning. In this section, we delve into the development of each module, including its architecture, underlying logic, and practical examples to showcase its capabilities.

3.1 COLD: The Metamodeling Foundation

The COLD framework serves as the foundational layer for creating standardized and semantically rich battery metamodels. A metamodel in this context is a digital representation of the structural and operational properties of a physical battery system. The goal of COLD is to provide a consistent and flexible mechanism for describing batteries, enabling interoperability and accurate digital representation. This was achieved using Pydantic to define class-based models that capture battery components, such as the cell casing, electrodes, active materials, and other key parameters.

3.1.1 Root Linked Data Model

The `LinkedDataModel` forms the foundation for all COLD models, enabling the creation of semantically rich, interoperable representations of batteries and their components. The code for the model is shown in Figure 1. Built with Pydantic, it provides a structured framework for defining key attributes like `class_name`, `class_iri`, `identifier`, `label`, and `comment`. These fields ensure alignment with domain ontologies such as the Battery Interface Ontology (BattINFO) and facilitate integration into linked data ecosystems. For example, the `class_name` and `class_iri` fields link instances to ontological definitions, while the `identifier`, aliased as `@id`, uniquely identifies instances within a broader context.

The model's hierarchical capabilities are encapsulated in the `hasProperty` field, which supports nested structures, allowing complex entities like batteries to include subcomponents such as electrodes or properties like voltage and capacity. This modularity ensures that representations are both comprehensive and semantically accurate.

A standout feature is its support for JSON-LD serialization through the `to_jsonld` method. This method converts the model into a standardized format for linked data, ensuring compatibility with semantic web technologies. The process excludes empty or irrelevant fields, while preserving nested structures for a clear and accurate representation of relationships. An optional `@context` field provides schema definitions, making the data reusable and interpretable across systems.

The `LinkedDataModel` ensures semantic consistency, facilitating error-free integration and reuse of battery models. Its hierarchical structure and robust serialization capabilities make it a cornerstone of the COLD framework, enabling detailed, interoperable digital representations essential for applications like digital twins and data sharing in battery research.

```
from pydantic import BaseModel, Field
from typing import Optional, List, Union

class LinkedDataModel(BaseModel):
    class_name: Optional[Union[str, List[str]]] = Field(None)
    class_iri: Optional[str] = Field(None)
    identifier: Optional[str] = Field(None, alias="@id")
    label: Optional[str] = Field(None, alias="rdfs:label")
    comment: Optional[Union[str, List[str]]] = Field(None,
alias="rdfs:comment")
    hasProperty: Optional[List[BaseModel]] = Field(default_factory=list)

class Config:
```

```

        populate_by_name = True # Enable alias population during
instantiation

    def to_jsonld(self, include_context=True) -> dict:
        """Custom JSON-LD serialization method."""
        jsonld_data = {}

        # Add context only at the top level
        if include_context:
            jsonld_data["@context"] =
"https://w3id.org/emmo/domain/battery/context"

        # Add @type for class_name if it exists
        if self.class_name:
            jsonld_data["@type"] = self.class_name

        # Process fields and exclude class_iri, class_name, and empty values
        for field_name, value in self.__dict__.items():
            if field_name in {"class_iri", "class_name"} or value is None or
value == []:
                continue # Skip class_iri, class_name, None, and empty
lists

            # Serialize nested LinkedDataModel instances
            if isinstance(value, LinkedDataModel):
                nested_jsonld = value.to_jsonld(include_context=False)
                if nested_jsonld: # Ensure the nested object is not empty
                    jsonld_data[field_name] = nested_jsonld
            elif isinstance(value, list):
                # Serialize lists of LinkedDataModel or other objects,
excluding empty lists
                nested_list = [
                    v.to_jsonld(include_context=False) if isinstance(v,
LinkedDataModel) else v
                    for v in value if v is not None
                ]
                if nested_list: # Add only non-empty lists
                    jsonld_data[field_name] = nested_list
            else:
                # Add scalar fields
                jsonld_data[field_name] = value

        return jsonld_data

```

Figure 1. Code for the foundational LinkedDataModel

Ontology-based Autogenerated Pydantic Models

What makes COLD particularly powerful is its automated generation of Pydantic models from BattINFO. The ontology, which adheres to widely recognized semantic web standards, defines a comprehensive vocabulary for describing batteries and their components. Using automated tools, the classes and properties defined in BattINFO are transformed into corresponding Pydantic models, ensuring that the metamodels remain aligned with the ontology. This approach eliminates manual errors, ensures semantic accuracy, and allows the framework to evolve alongside updates to the ontology.

For example, consider a CR2032 coin cell, a common battery type used in small-scale devices. The CR2032 metamodel encapsulates properties such as its diameter, thickness, capacity, and chemistry. By instantiating this metamodel, users can quickly establish a digital representation of the battery that aligns with real-world specifications. The class definition for the CR2032 cell in COLD looks as follows:

```
from pydantic import BaseModel, Field, validator, root_validator
from typing import Optional, List, Union
from .LithiumManganeseDioxideBatteryModule import
LithiumManganeseDioxideBattery
from .CoinCellModule import CoinCell
from .LithiumBasedElectrodeModule import LithiumBasedElectrode
from .OrganicElectrolyteModule import OrganicElectrolyte
from .R2032Module import R2032
from .ManganeseDioxideElectrodeModule import ManganeseDioxideElectrode
from .ThicknessModule import Thickness
from .DiameterModule import Diameter

class CR2032(LithiumManganeseDioxideBattery, CoinCell):

    class_iri: Optional[str] = Field(
        'https://w3id.org/emmo/domain/battery#battery_b61b96ac_f2f4_4b74_
_82d5_565fe3a2d88b',
        alias="class_iri"
    )

    class_name: Optional[str] = Field(
        'CR2032',
        alias="class_name"
    )

    hasNegativeElectrode: Optional[LithiumBasedElectrode] = Field(
        LithiumBasedElectrode(),
        alias="hasNegativeElectrode"
```

```

)

hasElectrolyte: Optional[OrganicElectrolyte] = Field(
    OrganicElectrolyte(),
    alias="hasElectrolyte"
)

hasCase: Optional[R2032] = Field(
    R2032(),
    alias="hasCase"
)

wikidataReference: Optional[str] = Field(
    None,
    alias="wikidataReference"
)

elucidation: Optional[str] = Field(
    None,
    alias="elucidation"
)

hasPositiveElectrode: Optional[ManganeseDioxideElectrode] =
Field(
    ManganeseDioxideElectrode(),
    alias="hasPositiveElectrode"
)

@validator("hasNegativeElectrode", pre=True, always=True)
def validate_hasNegativeElectrode(cls, value):
    if value is not None and not isinstance(value,
LithiumBasedElectrode):
        raise ValueError(f"Field 'hasNegativeElectrode' must be an
instance of 'LithiumBasedElectrode' or its subclass.")
    return value

@validator("hasElectrolyte", pre=True, always=True)
def validate_hasElectrolyte(cls, value):
    if value is not None and not isinstance(value, OrganicElectrolyte):
        raise ValueError(f"Field 'hasElectrolyte' must be an instance of
'OrganicElectrolyte' or its subclass.")
    return value

@validator("hasCase", pre=True, always=True)
def validate_hasCase(cls, value):
    if value is not None and not isinstance(value, R2032):

```

```

        raise ValueError(f"Field 'hasCase' must be an instance of
'R2032' or its subclass.")
    return value

    @validator("hasPositiveElectrode", pre=True, always=True)
    def validate_hasPositiveElectrode(cls, value):
        if value is not None and not isinstance(value,
ManganeseDioxideElectrode):
            raise ValueError(f"Field 'hasPositiveElectrode' must be an
instance of 'ManganeseDioxideElectrode' or its subclass.")
        return value

    @root_validator(pre=True)
    def set_defaults(cls, values):
        values["hasProperty"] = values.get("hasProperty", [
            Diameter(0.020, "Metre"),
            Thickness(0.0032, "Metre")
        ])

    return values

```

Figure 2. Code for the CR2032 model, auto-generated from the BattINFO ontology

3.1.2 Built-In Validation

The Pydantic model for the CR2032 cell, shown above, illustrates how the COLD framework integrates inherent validation mechanisms to ensure the integrity and consistency of the data being represented. This validation capability is one of the key advantages of using Pydantic for creating battery metamodels. Each field in the model, such as `hasNegativeElectrode`, `hasElectrolyte`, `hasCase`, and `hasPositiveElectrode`, is not only explicitly typed but also validated through custom validators. These validators enforce strict type conformity and ensure that each field is assigned a value that matches its expected type or subclass.

For example, the `hasNegativeElectrode` field is expected to be an instance of `LithiumBasedElectrode` or its subclass. The corresponding validator raises an error if an incompatible type is assigned, preventing invalid or inconsistent data from being propagated through the system. Similarly, the `hasElectrolyte` field must be an instance of `OrganicElectrolyte`, ensuring that only appropriate materials are modeled as electrolytes in the CR2032 metamodel. These validations are executed automatically whenever the model is instantiated or updated, safeguarding the data structure from errors and improving its reliability.

In addition to field-level validation, the use of a `root_validator` provides a mechanism to enforce rules across multiple fields or to apply default settings to the entire model. In this

example, the `set_defaults` root validator ensures that properties like `Diameter` and `Thickness` are always included as part of the `CR2032` description. This guarantees that essential attributes are never omitted, even if they are not explicitly provided by the user during instantiation.

Moreover, the `Pydantic` framework also provides mechanisms for aliasing and serialization. For instance, fields such as `class_iri` and `class_name` use aliases to maintain consistency with external naming conventions, ensuring that the serialized JSON-LD output adheres to expected schemas. This built-in flexibility facilitates seamless integration of the models with semantic web tools, ontologies, and other frameworks that depend on structured and validated data.

The inherent validation capabilities of `Pydantic` not only enhance the robustness of the `COLD` framework but also provide significant benefits for downstream applications. By ensuring that each metamodel is both syntactically correct and semantically valid, the system reduces the likelihood of errors in analysis, simulation, or data exchange. Furthermore, the automated validation process eliminates the need for manual checks, streamlining workflows and improving efficiency. This makes `COLD` a reliable foundation for building digital twins, as it guarantees that the structural representations of batteries are accurate, complete, and aligned with domain-specific ontological standards.

3.1.3 RDF Serialization Support

By serializing the metamodel using JSON-LD, the representation can be stored, shared, or integrated into other tools seamlessly. For instance, the `CR2032` metamodel could be serialized as:

```
{
  "@context": "https://w3id.org/emmo/domain/battery/context",
  "@type": "CR2032",
  "hasProperty": [
    {
      "@type": "Diameter",
      "hasNumericalPart": {
        "@type": "Real",
        "hasNumericalValue": 0.02
      },
      "hasMeasurementUnit": {
        "@type": "Metre"
      }
    },
    {
      "@type": "Thickness",
      "hasNumericalPart": {
        "@type": "Real",
```

```

        "hasNumericalValue": 0.0032
      },
      "hasMeasurementUnit": {
        "@type": "Metre"
      }
    }
  ],
  "hasNegativeElectrode": {
    "@type": "LithiumBasedElectrode"
  },
  "hasPositiveElectrode": {
    "@type": "ManganeseDioxideElectrode"
  },
  "hasElectrolyte": {
    "@type": "OrganicElectrolyte"
  },
  "hasCase": {
    "@type": "R2032"
  }
}

```

Figure 3. Example JSON-LD serialization from CR2032 model

This standardized description can be reused in simulations, optimizations, and other downstream analyses. In a real-world scenario, the digital twin might combine this structural data with live performance data, such as voltage and current, to assess how the CR2032 behaves under load conditions.

COLD also allows users to extend or customize models to define new battery types. For example, if a lithium-ion pouch cell requires additional properties, these attributes can be added dynamically. The use of Pydantic ensures that all models are validated and serialized consistently, reducing the potential for errors.

3.2 GLEANED: Harvesting Static and Live Data

Once the metamodel is established, the GLEANED framework provides the tools necessary to interface with real-world data. GLEANED was designed to support both static data sources, such as CSV and Parquet files, and live data streams, such as WMI-based system monitoring or API integrations. This flexibility ensures that the digital twin framework can operate seamlessly across a variety of use cases, from analyzing historical test results to performing real-time monitoring of battery systems.

3.2.1 Root DataHarvester Class

The core of GLEANED is the DataHarvester, a class responsible for managing data sources and providing a unified interface for data collection. The harvester registers data sources

and exposes methods for retrieving static data, polling live data at fixed intervals, or continuously streaming updates. The architecture of GLEANED allows users to register multiple data sources and switch between them without significant reconfiguration.

The DataHarvester class is the central component of the GLEANED framework, designed to facilitate efficient and modular data collection from various sources. Its primary purpose is to manage data harvesting workflows, enabling seamless integration of static files, live streams, and system-monitoring tools. By encapsulating common data collection functionalities, the DataHarvester simplifies user interaction while maintaining flexibility and extensibility for diverse applications. A sample of the code used to define the DataHarvester model is shown in Figure 4.

At its core, the DataHarvester maintains a registry of data sources and their corresponding collected data. Each data source is represented as an instance of the DataSource class or its subclasses, which define the specific methods for data collection and metadata retrieval. When a new source is registered using the register_source method, it is added to the internal registry, and a placeholder DataFrame is initialized to store its collected data. This mechanism ensures that the harvester can dynamically accommodate multiple sources, regardless of their type or collection method.

The harvesting functionality is implemented through several key methods, each tailored to specific use cases. The harvest_static method is designed for static data sources, such as CSV or Parquet files, that do not change over time. This method calls the source's collect_data function, retrieves the data, and returns it as a DataFrame. This straightforward approach is ideal for loading historical datasets or pre-recorded measurements.

For live data collection, the DataHarvester provides methods such as harvest_live and harvest_live_and_print, which allow users to collect data continuously over a specified duration. These methods leverage a source's collect_data function in a loop, ensuring data is retrieved at regular intervals defined by the source's refresh_interval. During live harvesting, the collected data is either printed to the console, stored internally, or serialized to a file, depending on user preferences. The modular design of these methods makes it easy to extend the framework for additional functionalities, such as live visualization or data streaming.

The get_live_status method offers a snapshot capability, providing a one-time view of the current status of a live data source. By retrieving a single instance of data, this method is particularly useful for real-time diagnostics or quick status checks. The returned data is formatted as a dictionary, making it easily consumable for downstream applications or APIs.

Another critical feature of the DataHarvester is its ability to manage live harvesting through threading. The _stop_flag event is shared across all live harvesting threads,

allowing the harvester to gracefully terminate ongoing data collection processes. This ensures that live data harvesting can be controlled dynamically, even in long-running or continuous workflows.

To support the export of collected data, the `_serialize_data` method provides a flexible mechanism for saving data to various formats, including CSV, Parquet, and JSON. This functionality ensures that users can persist their collected data in a format suitable for further analysis, sharing, or integration with external tools.

The design of the DataHarvester emphasizes usability and adaptability. By abstracting the complexities of data collection into a single, unified interface, it empowers users to focus on their analysis rather than the mechanics of data retrieval. Its extensible architecture allows new data sources to be integrated seamlessly, ensuring the framework remains relevant for emerging technologies and use cases.

```
import pandas as pd
import threading
import time
from typing import Callable, Optional
from gleaned.datasources.base import DataSource

class DataHarvester:
    def __init__(self):
        self.sources = []
        self.collected_data = {}
        self._stop_flag = threading.Event() # Shared flag to stop live
harvesting threads

    def register_source(self, sources):
        """
        Register one or more data sources.
        :param sources: A single data source or a list of data sources.
        """
        if not isinstance(sources, list):
            sources = [sources]

        for source in sources:
            self.sources.append(source)
            self.collected_data[source.metadata()["source"]] =
pd.DataFrame()
            print(f"Registered source: {source.metadata()['source']}")

    def harvest_static(self, source: DataSource) -> pd.DataFrame:
        """
        Harvest static data from a registered source.
        :param source: The data source object.
        :return: A DataFrame containing the harvested data.
```

```

        """
        print(f"Harvesting static data from source:
{source.metadata()['source']}")
        data = source.collect_data()
        if data.empty:
            print(f"No data collected from {source.metadata()['source']}.")
        else:
            print(f"Collected {len(data)} rows from
{source.metadata()['source']}.")
        return data

    def harvest_live(
        self,
        source_name: str,
        duration: int,
        serialize_path: Optional[str] = None,
        print_data: bool = False
    ):
        """
        Harvest live data for a specified duration.
        :param source_name: Name of the data source.
        :param duration: Duration in seconds for data collection.
        :param serialize_path: Path to save the data (optional).
        :param print_data: Whether to print collected data to the console.
        """
        source = self._get_source_by_name(source_name)
        print(f"Starting live data harvesting for {duration} seconds from
source: {source_name}")
        start_time = time.time()

        while time.time() - start_time < duration and not
self._stop_flag.is_set():
            try:
                data = source.collect_data()
                if not data.empty:
                    if print_data:
                        print(f"Collected {len(data)} rows from
{source_name}:")
                        print(data)

                        # Store collected data
                        self.collected_data[source.metadata()["source"]] =
pd.concat(
                            [self.collected_data[source.metadata()["source"]],
data], ignore_index=True
                        )
            else:

```

```

        print(f"No data collected this cycle from
{source_name}.")
        except Exception as e:
            print(f"Error while collecting data: {e}")
            time.sleep(source.refresh_interval)

        if serialize_path:
            self._serialize_data(source.metadata()["source"],
serialize_path)
            print(f"Data saved to {serialize_path}")

    print("Live data harvesting complete.")

def harvest_live_and_print(self, source_name: str, duration: int):
    """
    Harvest live data for a specified duration and print the values.
    :param source_name: Name of the data source.
    :param duration: Duration in seconds for data collection.
    """
    source = self._get_source_by_name(source_name)
    print(f"Starting live data harvesting for {duration} seconds from
source: {source_name}")
    start_time = time.time()

    while time.time() - start_time < duration and not
self._stop_flag.is_set():
        try:
            data = source.collect_data()
            if not data.empty():
                print(f"Collected {len(data)} rows from {source_name}:")
                print(data)
            else:
                print(f"No data collected this cycle from
{source_name}.")
        except Exception as e:
            print(f"Error while collecting data: {e}")
            time.sleep(source.refresh_interval)

    print("Live data harvesting complete.")

def get_live_status(self, source_name: str) -> dict:
    """
    Get a one-time snapshot of the live status from a data source.
    :param source_name: Name of the data source.
    :return: A dictionary with the collected values or an empty
dictionary if no data is collected.

```

```

"""
    source = self._get_source_by_name(source_name)
    print(f"Taking a snapshot of the live status from source:
{source_name}")

    try:
        data = source.collect_data()
        if not data.empty:
            print(f"Snapshot collected with {len(data)} rows:")
            print(data)
            # Convert the first row of the dataframe to a dictionary
            return data.iloc[0].to_dict()
        else:
            print(f"No data collected from source: {source_name}")
    except Exception as e:
        print(f"Error while collecting snapshot: {e}")

    return {}

def stop_harvesting(self):
    """Signal to stop all live harvesting."""
    print("Stopping live harvesting...")
    self._stop_flag.set()

def _get_source_by_name(self, source_name: str):
    """Retrieve a registered source by its name."""
    for source in self.sources:
        if source.metadata()["source"] == source_name:
            return source
    raise ValueError(f"Source {source_name} not found.")

def _serialize_data(self, source_name: str, file_path: str):
    """Save collected data to a file."""
    data = self.collected_data.get(source_name, pd.DataFrame())
    if data.empty:
        print(f"No data available for source: {source_name}")
        return

    try:
        if file_path.endswith(".csv"):
            data.to_csv(file_path, index=False)
        elif file_path.endswith(".parquet"):
            data.to_parquet(file_path)
        elif file_path.endswith(".json"):
            data.to_json(file_path, orient="records")
        else:
            raise ValueError(f"Unsupported file format for {file_path}")

```

```

    print(f"Data saved to {file_path}.")
except Exception as e:
    print(f"Error while saving data to {file_path}: {e}")

```

Figure 4. Code for the foundational class DataHarvester

3.2.2 Example of Combined Data Harvesting

This example, shown in Figure 5, illustrates the flexibility and capability of the GLEANED framework, showcasing how the DataHarvester class integrates data from both static and live sources. The workflow demonstrates the registration of multiple data sources, static data harvesting, and live data collection, providing a clear picture of how GLEANED can be used for diverse data acquisition tasks.

```

import os
from gleaned.harvester import DataHarvester
from gleaned.datasources.file_source import FileSource
from gleaned.datasources.wmi_source import WMIDataSource

# Initialize the harvester
harvester = DataHarvester()

# Define the file path for the file
extension = "json"
file_name = os.path.abspath(f"battery_data.{extension}") # Convert to
absolute path
print(f"Using file: {file_name}")

# Register the file source
file_source = FileSource(file_path=file_name, file_type=f"{extension}")
wmi_source = WMIDataSource(refresh_interval=1)
harvester.register_source([file_source, wmi_source])

# Use the exact source name
data = harvester.harvest_static(file_source)
if not data.empty:
    print(data.head()) # Display the first few rows
else:
    print("No data collected from the file.")

# Start live harvesting
print("Harvesting live data for 3 seconds and saving to file...")
harvester.harvest_live("BatteryStatus via WMI", duration=5, print_data=True)

```

Figure 5. Code for example combined data harvesting

Setting Up the Harvester and Data Sources

The script begins by initializing the DataHarvester, which serves as the central manager for all data collection activities. Two data sources are then registered:

- **FileSource:** A static data source that reads data from a file. In this example, the file type is dynamically set to JSON, and its absolute path is determined using Python's `os.path` module. This ensures the file can be accessed regardless of the current working directory.
- **WMIDataSource:** A live data source that polls battery-related information from the system using Windows Management Instrumentation (WMI). This source is configured with a refresh interval of one second, making it suitable for real-time monitoring.

The `register_source` method of the DataHarvester is used to register both sources in a single command. Each source is automatically validated and prepared for data collection.

Harvesting Static Data

The first operation demonstrates the harvesting of static data from the registered file source. The `harvest_static` method is called with the `file_source` object, triggering the FileSource class to read data from the specified JSON file. If the file contains valid data, it is loaded into a Pandas DataFrame, and the first few rows are printed to the console for verification. If no data is found, an appropriate message is displayed.

This functionality is particularly useful for loading historical datasets or pre-recorded measurements, which can be used as a baseline for analysis or comparison with live data.

Harvesting Live Data

Next, the script showcases the live data harvesting capabilities of GLEAINED. The `BatteryStatus` class in the `root\WMI` namespace provides real-time information about the machine's battery, such as voltage, remaining capacity, discharge rate, and charge rate.

Using the `harvest_live` method, data is collected from the WMI DataSource for a duration of five seconds. During this period, the system polls the WMI source every second, collecting real-time information about the battery status. Each collected batch of data is printed to the console, providing immediate feedback about the ongoing collection process.

This live harvesting functionality is ideal for scenarios requiring real-time monitoring or diagnostics. By setting the `print_data` parameter to `True`, the user can observe the data as it is collected, enabling quick assessments of system performance or behavior.

Example Output

The script is designed to handle a variety of scenarios, including missing or invalid data, ensuring robust and reliable data collection. A typical output, Figure 6, might look like this:

```
Registered source: JSON File
Registered source: BatteryStatus via WMI

Collected 5 rows from JSON File:
      Timestamp  TestTime / s  ...  Discharge Rate / W  Charge
Rate / W
0 2024-12-09
22:09:16.080      0.028510  ...      NaN      NaN
1 2024-12-09
22:09:17.109      1.057472  ...      NaN      NaN
2 2024-12-09
22:09:18.140      2.088808  ...      NaN      NaN
3 2024-12-09
22:09:19.177      3.126328  ...      NaN      NaN
4 2024-12-09
22:09:20.217      4.165516  ...      NaN      NaN

Starting live data harvesting for 5 seconds from source: BatteryStatus via WMI
Collected 1 rows from BatteryStatus via WMI:
      Timestamp  TestTime / s  ...  Discharge Rate / W  Charge
Rate / W
0 2024-12-15
22:12:22.291136      0.051961  ...      None      None
0 2024-12-15
22:12:23.323611      1.084436  ...      None      None
0 2024-12-15
22:12:24.375470      2.136295  ...      None      None
0 2024-12-15
22:12:25.401277      3.162102  ...      None      None
0 2024-12-15
22:12:26.427494      4.188319  ...      None      None
```

Figure 6. Example output of combined data harvesting

The modular design of GLEANED makes it easy to add support for new data sources. For example, a ParquetSource or JSONSource can be implemented similarly to the CSVSource, while APIs or IoT devices can be integrated through HTTP-based polling mechanisms. This extensibility ensures that the digital twin can adapt to evolving requirements and data formats.

3.3 ECHOED: Orchestrating the Digital Twin

The ECHOED framework ties together the battery metamodel from COLD and the data collected through GLEANED to create a fully functional digital twin. ECHOED provides a high-level interface for instantiating and interacting with digital twins, making it possible to monitor live performance, analyze historical data, and connect with simulations or optimization tools.

3.3.1 Root DigitalTwin Class

The DigitalTwin class, shown in Figure 7, in the ECHOED framework represents a central component for managing and interacting with the digital twin of a battery. It combines a detailed metamodel that captures the physical and operational characteristics of the battery with robust data harvesting capabilities to ensure seamless integration of real-world and simulated data streams. Designed to be intuitive and flexible, the DigitalTwin class enables researchers and engineers to bridge the gap between physical systems and their digital counterparts.

```
import pandas as pd
import os
from gleaned import DataHarvester, FileSource, WMIDataSource

class DigitalTwin:
    """
    DigitalTwin class for representing and managing a digital twin of a
    battery.

    Attributes:
        metamodel (object): The metamodel instance representing the battery.
        data_sources (list): A list of data sources associated with the
        digital twin.
        harvester (DataHarvester): A harvester instance for managing data
        collection.
    """

    def __init__(self, metamodel, data_sources=None):
        """
        Initialize the DigitalTwin.

        :param metamodel: The metamodel representing the battery.
        :param data_sources: A list of data sources (optional).
        """
        self.metamodel = metamodel
        self.harvester = DataHarvester()
```

```

self.data_sources = data_sources or []

# Register all provided data sources
for source in self.data_sources:
    self.harvester.register_source(source)

def harvest_static_data(self, source_name):
    """
    Harvest static data from a registered source.

    :param source_name: Name of the source to harvest data from.
    :return: DataFrame containing the harvested data.
    """
    print(f"Harvesting static data from source: {source_name}")
    return self.harvester.harvest_static(source_name)

def harvest_live_data(self, source_name, duration, serialize_path=None):
    """
    Harvest live data from a source for a specific duration.

    :param source_name: Name of the source to harvest data from.
    :param duration: Duration (in seconds) for live data harvesting.
    :param serialize_path: Path to serialize the collected data
    (optional).
    """
    print(f"Starting live data harvesting from source: {source_name}")
    self.harvester.harvest_live_by_interval(source_name, duration,
    serialize_path)

def get_live_status(self, source_name=None):
    """
    Get a snapshot of the current live status from a source.

    :param source_name: Name of the source to get status from. If not
    provided,
        it defaults to the first registered live source.
    :return: Dictionary with the live status values.
    """
    if not source_name:
        # Find the first live source if no source_name is provided
        live_sources = [source for source in self.harvester.sources if
        source.refresh_interval > 0]
        if live_sources:
            source_name = live_sources[0].metadata()["source"]
            print(f"No source_name provided. Defaulting to live source:
            {source_name}")
        else:

```

```

        raise ValueError("No live sources registered, and no
source_name provided.")

    print(f"Getting live status from source: {source_name}")
    return self.harvester.get_live_status(source_name)

def register_new_source(self, source):
    """
    Register a new data source.

    :param source: The data source to register.
    """
    print(f"Registering new data source: {source.metadata()['source']}")
    self.data_sources.append(source)
    self.harvester.register_source(source)

def describe(self):
    """
    Print a summary of the Digital Twin.

    :return: None
    """
    print("=== Digital Twin Summary ===")
    print(f"Metamodel: {self.metamodel}")
    print("Registered Data Sources:")
    for source in self.data_sources:
        print(f"  - {source.metadata()['source']}")

def serialize_metamodel(self, file_path):
    """
    Serialize the metamodel to a file.

    :param file_path: Path to save the serialized metamodel.
    """
    print(f"Serializing metamodel to: {file_path}")
    with open(file_path, "w") as f:
        f.write(str(self.metamodel))
    print("Metamodel serialized successfully.")

```

Figure 7. Code for the root DigitalTwin class

At its core, the DigitalTwin encapsulates three primary elements: the metamodel, data sources, and a data harvester. The metamodel is a structured representation of the battery, containing detailed information about its components, properties, and relationships. This serves as the foundation for creating a semantically rich and machine-readable description of the battery, which aligns with domain ontologies like those in the

COLD framework. For instance, a metamodel for a CR2032 cell might include details about its electrodes, electrolyte, casing, and capacity, offering a digital equivalent of the physical battery.

The data sources registered with the DigitalTwin act as the interface for integrating external data streams. These can include static sources, such as historical data stored in CSV or Parquet files, as well as live sources, such as system-level monitoring via WMI. By registering these sources, the DigitalTwin can dynamically collect and manage data, providing users with a comprehensive view of the battery's current state and historical performance.

The DataHarvester, a component of the GLEANED framework, serves as the backbone for managing data collection. It abstracts the complexities of data harvesting, allowing the DigitalTwin to focus on higher-level operations. Key functionalities of the DigitalTwin class include the ability to harvest static and live data. The `harvest_static_data` method enables users to retrieve data from a specified static source, such as test results or experimental measurements. This data can be loaded into a Pandas DataFrame for immediate analysis, making it easy to incorporate historical records into the twin's operational context. On the other hand, the `harvest_live_data` method facilitates real-time monitoring by collecting data continuously over a defined duration. This live data can be serialized for later use or printed directly for real-time assessment, providing actionable insights into the battery's performance.

The `get_live_status` method offers another valuable feature, allowing users to take a snapshot of the current state of a live data source. If no source name is provided, the method intelligently defaults to the first registered live source, ensuring a seamless user experience. This capability is particularly useful for diagnostics or on-the-fly evaluations of the battery's behavior.

Another important feature of the DigitalTwin is its extensibility. Users can easily add new data sources with the `register_new_source` method, enabling the twin to adapt to evolving requirements or additional data streams. This flexibility ensures that the twin remains a robust tool for a wide range of applications, from real-time system monitoring to advanced analytics.

In addition to managing data, the DigitalTwin supports serialization of its metamodel through the `serialize_metamodel` method. This allows users to export the metamodel to a file for documentation, sharing, or integration into other tools. Combined with its `describe` method, which provides a concise summary of the twin and its registered sources, the DigitalTwin class ensures transparency and ease of use.

The design of the DigitalTwin class reflects the broader goals of the ECHOED framework: to create an intuitive, interoperable, and extensible digital twin solution for battery systems. By combining the rich descriptive capabilities of the metamodel with the data

harvesting power of GLEANED, the DigitalTwin provides a unified platform for understanding, simulating, and optimizing battery performance in real-world and virtual environments. Its modular architecture and user-friendly interface make it a valuable tool for advancing research, enabling predictive maintenance, and fostering innovation in the energy storage domain.

3.3.2 Example Usage

This example, shown in Figure 8, showcases the process of creating and using a DigitalTwin object within the ECHOED framework. The digital twin is designed to digitally represent a CR2032 coin cell battery, integrating both live and static data sources to enable real-time monitoring and comprehensive analysis. We have selected the CR2032 coin cell as an example metamodel; however, any appropriate battery type could be used for the data source.

```
import os
from cold.models import autogenerated as cold
from gleaned import DataHarvester, FileSource, WMIDataSource
from echoed import base
import json

# Create a digital twin
my_twin = base.DigitalTwin(
    metamodel = cold.CR2032(),
    data_sources = [
        WMIDataSource(refresh_interval = 1),
        FileSource(file_path=os.path.abspath("battery_data.parquet"),
file_type="parquet"),
        FileSource(file_path=os.path.abspath("battery_data.csv"),
file_type="csv"),
        FileSource(file_path=os.path.abspath("battery_data.json"),
file_type="json")
    ]
)

print("Digital twin initialized:", my_twin)

data = my_twin.get_live_status()

json_ld = my_twin.metamodel.to_jsonld()
print(json.dumps(json_ld, indent=4))
```

Figure 8. Example usage of DigitalTwin class

The first step involves initializing the digital twin with a metamodel that captures the structural and operational properties of the battery. Using the COLD framework, the CR2032 model is loaded to define the battery's key attributes in a semantically rich

manner. This metamodel provides the foundation for the digital twin, ensuring its representation aligns with established battery domain ontologies.

The digital twin is then connected to multiple data sources, including a live data source that uses Windows Management Instrumentation (WMI) to collect real-time data at one-second intervals. Additionally, static data sources are registered to read battery-related data from files in formats such as Parquet, CSV, and JSON. These static sources complement the live data stream by providing historical records or pre-recorded datasets, enhancing the twin's ability to analyze and simulate battery performance across different timeframes.

Once the digital twin is set up, its functionality can be demonstrated by retrieving live data from the WMI source. A snapshot of the battery's current state is obtained using the `get_live_status` method, which queries the live data source to provide up-to-date information. This might include real-time metrics such as voltage, remaining capacity, and charge or discharge rates, depending on the data source's capabilities. This feature highlights the digital twin's role as a dynamic representation of the battery, continuously linked to the physical system it models.

Another important aspect of the digital twin is its ability to serialize its metamodel into JSON-LD format. This capability allows the detailed structure of the CR2032 battery to be represented in a standardized and interoperable format. The serialized data is both human-readable and machine-interpretable, making it suitable for integration with other tools or platforms, as well as for creating linked data graphs or conducting semantic analysis. The resulting JSON-LD output captures the relationships and properties of the battery in a way that aligns with modern data-sharing standards.

The process illustrated in this example highlights the potential of digital twins to unify live and historical data into a coherent and actionable representation of physical systems. By enabling seamless interaction between live data sources and static records, the digital twin supports advanced use cases, including real-time diagnostics, performance tracking, and predictive modeling. The ECHOED framework, through its modular and extensible design, demonstrates its capacity to create sophisticated digital twins for batteries, integrating metamodeling, data harvesting, and advanced analysis in a unified workflow.

4. Summary and Future Work

The development of the digital twin framework presented in this report showcases a modular, extensible, and integrated approach to modelling, monitoring, and analyzing battery systems. By combining the structural precision of COLD (metamodeling), the real-world data integration of GLEANED (data harvesting), and the orchestration capabilities of ECHOED (digital twin framework), this system represents a significant step forward in creating actionable and dynamic digital representations of batteries.

4.1 Summary

The framework's foundation in semantic web technologies ensures that all components align with standards like JSON-LD and RDF, enabling interoperability across tools and systems. The metamodels in COLD allow for detailed, standardized descriptions of battery systems that can evolve with the inclusion of new ontologies. These metamodels not only support automated validation but also facilitate error-free integration into simulations and analytics workflows.

Meanwhile, GLEANED bridges the gap between static datasets, such as experimental logs or historical records, and live streams from monitoring systems, such as WMI. Its DataHarvester class simplifies the process of collecting, managing, and serializing data from diverse sources, ensuring that real-time and historical data can seamlessly coexist. The ECHOED framework builds on this foundation, offering an intuitive interface for creating and interacting with digital twins. The framework supports live monitoring, static data analysis, and real-time system diagnostics, making it adaptable to a wide range of research and industrial scenarios.

The flexibility and modularity demonstrated in example use cases, such as real-time performance monitoring of a cell, highlight the potential of this framework to revolutionize workflows in battery research. By unifying live and static data within a semantic and standardized framework, the system enables real-time diagnostics, historical analysis, and predictive capabilities.

4.2 Future Work

The next phase of development will focus on expanding the capabilities of the digital twin framework, particularly in the integration of simulation and optimization tools. PyBOP, a parameterization and optimization framework, will be incorporated to enable users to calibrate models against experimental data and optimize design parameters. Coupling with simulation platforms like BattMo and PyBaMM will extend the framework's predictive modeling capabilities. These integrations will allow researchers to test scenarios virtually, such as degradation modelling or lifecycle predictions, enhancing the decision-making process.

Another critical area for development is the enrichment of data harvesting capabilities. Additional sources, such as IoT sensors or cloud-based APIs, will be integrated, enabling the framework to support a broader range of operational environments. Enhancements in visualization and user interfaces will also improve accessibility, providing real-time dashboards and analytics for monitoring and exploring twin performance.

Finally, efforts will focus on scaling the framework for industrial use. This includes refining the architecture to handle larger datasets and ensuring compatibility with enterprise-

grade systems. Through these advancements, the digital twin framework aims to transform battery research and management, bridging the gap between experimentation, simulation, and real-world deployment.

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